

AGRIN HAS A PATHOLOGICAL ROLE IN THE PROGRESSION OF ORAL CANCER

Running title: Agrin promotes the progression of oral cancer

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: The extracellular matrix modulates the hallmarks of cancer. Here, we examined the role of agrin -a member of this matrix- in progression of oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC).

METHODS: We evaluated the immunohistochemical expression of agrin in OSCC and dysplasias. Benign lesions were used as control. In subsequent experiments, we investigated whether the silencing of agrin interferes with tumor expansion, both, *in vitro* as well as *in vivo*. To gain insights into the role of agrin, we identified its protein network (interactome) using mass spectrometry-based proteomics and bioinformatics. Finally, we evaluated the clinical relevance of agrin interactome.

RESULTS: Agrin was elevated in malignant and premalignant lesions. Further, we show that agrin silencing interferes with cancer cell motility, proliferation, invasion, colony and tumor spheroid formation, and it also reduces the phosphorylation of FAK, ERK and cyclin D1 proteins in OSCC cells. In orthotopic model, agrin silencing reduces tumor aggressiveness, like vascular and neural invasion. From a clinical perspective, agrin contextual hubs predict a poor clinical prognosis related with overall survival.

CONCLUSIONS: Altogether, our results demonstrate that agrin is a histological marker for the progression of oral cancer and is a strong therapeutic target candidate for both premalignant and OSCC lesions.

Keywords: Agrin; mouth neoplasms; oral cancer; head and neck cancer; biomarkers, tumor; proteomics; protein interaction maps.

INTRODUCTION

Worldwide, head and neck squamous cell carcinoma (HNSCC) affects over 500,000 patients per year ([Torre et al, 2015](#)). Oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC) represents 95% of all forms of HNSCC ([Rivera, 2015](#)). It is the most common malignancy of the head and neck ([Chi et al, 2015](#)). Despite advancements in prevention and multimodality therapies, the prognosis of OSCC patients has remained unfavorable in the last few decades ([Rivera et al, 2017](#)). A better understanding of cellular and molecular mechanisms that promote the progression of OSCC can help improve our approach to this disease.

The process of cancer progression (i.e., local invasion and metastasis) is characterized by rapid cellular growth accompanied by alterations of the microenvironment of the cancer cells ([Vaupel, 2004](#)). OSCC can be presented as a natural history, which originates from nontumorigenic keratinocytes which are chronically exposed to carcinogens, following a hyperplasia, oral epithelial dysplasia (in different degrees) and an invasive carcinoma leading to the generation of metastases ([Tanaka & Ishigamori, 2011](#)).

The extracellular matrix (ECM) modulates the hallmarks of cancer, and changes in its dynamics contribute to tumor progression ([Pickup et al, 2014](#)). Some components of the ECM, which include heparan sulfate proteoglycans, are frequently overproduced in cancer ([Lu et al, 2012](#)). Agrin is one of the main heparan sulfate proteoglycans present in the ECM.

Agrin is a multi-domain protein expressed as either a membrane protein or secreted in the ECM ([Chakraborty et al, 2015](#)). Agrin has been shown to act as a sensor in developing oncogenic signals associated with the ECM in hepatic carcinomas

([Chakraborty et al., 2015](#)). In the context of OSCC progression, a previous study of our group showed agrin has high expression in OSCC and has a role on cell migration, adhesion and resistance to chemotherapy ([Kawahara et al., 2014a](#)), suggesting that agrin also has an oncogenic role in oral cancer.

Agrin can be proteolytically cleaved, which generates bioactive fragments that modulate cellular behavior ([Neill et al., 2015](#)). One of the agrin cleavage products, the C-terminal fragment (hereafter called Ct-agrin), has been shown to be a promising new biomarker for pathological processes including sarcopenia ([Scherbakov et al., 2016](#)), renal dysfunction ([Yu et al., 2017](#)) and colorectal cancer ([Klein-Scory et al., 2010](#)). The disintegration of the basement membrane upon local invasion processes can release agrin processing products such as Ct-agrin ([Klein-Scory et al., 2010](#)). Within OSCC are active proteases, such as MMP-3 and neurotrypsin ([Hardt et al., 2011](#); [Wiegand et al., 2005](#)), which are capable of generating this soluble fragment. Focusing on the dynamics of tumor progression, the Ct-agrin could then help explain the role of agrin in oral cancer.

Despite the findings from the aforementioned studies, the contribution of agrin to cancer progression remains unknown. To better understand the role of this protein in OSCC, we studied the immunohistochemistry staining of agrin in benign, premalignant (oral epithelial dysplasias, OEDs) and malignant lesions. In addition, we modulated the expression of agrin in aberrant keratinocytes and evaluated processes and characteristics associated with cancer progression *in vitro* and *in vivo*. Considering the potential of Ct-agrin, we identified its binding proteins (interactome) in an OSCC context using mass spectrometry-based proteomics and bioinformatics. Finally, we found that agrin interactome is related with clinical outcomes of head and neck cancers.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Ethical statement. All procedures were in accordance with the Helsinki Declaration and the guidelines for the welfare and use of animals in cancer research ([Workman et al., 2010](#)). This research was approved by the Ethics Committee of FOP-UNICAMP (CAAE protocol #78069317.0.0000.5418) and the Animal Ethics Committee CEUA-CNPEM (protocol #13-2015).

General design. In the first experiment, we evaluated agrin immunoexpression on tissue biopsies. The effect of agrin silencing in cancer events was evaluated by *in vitro* and *in vivo* (orthotopic model) experiments. We induced the overexpression of secreted agrin fragment and ligands able to bind it were identified by mass spectrometry after protein immunoprecipitation. Once the agrin ligands were identified, we visualize the agrin network and evaluate its potential prognostic value.

Subjects:

Patients. We retrospectively collected OSCCs (n=58), OEDs (n=40) and benign lesions (n=35) from two oral pathology services (University of Talca and University of Campinas). The information of patients is provided in Supplementary Table S1.

Cells. The following cell lines were used: HMK and HaCaT (nontumorigenic human keratinocytes), SCC-9 and SCC-25 (OSCC), HSC-3 and SCC-9-LN1 (highly invasive and metastatic OSCC cells), and HEK-293 (variable tumorigenic potential). All cells were cultured in recommended media, under standard conditions (Supplementary Table

S2). HaCaT, SCC9 and HSC-3 were used to establish agrin-silenced cells. The HEK-293 cell line was used to establish cells that overexpress secreted agrin.

Mice. Age matched NOD-SCID male mice (6–weeks old) were obtained under specific pathogen-free conditions (FMUSP, São Paulo, Brazil). Animals were maintained under controlled conditions with freely available food and water, in groups of 4 mice each.

Procedures:

Measuring agrin expression in oral lesions. Immunostaining was performed using the sodium citrate standard protocol for antigen retrieval. Primary antibody used was an agrin antibody (1:300 dilution; #374117, Santa Cruz). Staining was quantified using the IHC profiler plugin in ImageJ ([Varghese et al, 2014](#)). Additionally, IHC slides were evaluated by two pathologists blinded to clinical data who provided a consensus opinion of staining patterns by light microscopy. According to the consensus, we described intensity (signal strength) and geographical spread. Intensity was classified as 0=negative, 1=low, 2=positive and 3=high. Geographical spread was classified as 0=no epithelial staining, 1=lower third, 2=two thirds or more and 3=full thickness. For relative risk (RR) analysis, grades 0–1 were merged into the ‘level 1’ group and grades 2–3 were labelled as ‘level 2’. Briefly, RR corresponded to the proportion of cancer or premalignant lesions in cases with higher expression of agrin divided by the proportion of cancer or premalignant lesions in cases with lower expression.

Generation of agrin silenced cells. We performed agrin (isoform 1, also known as secreted agrin) silencing studies using short hairpin RNA (shRNA)-expressing vectors.

We cloned agrin shRNA constructs #TRCN0000056390 and #TRCN0000056391 (RNAi Consortium) into pLKO.1-TRC plasmid (Addgene #10878). We chose the first target for functional experiments (target and template sequences shared a complete alignment). pLKO.1-shGFP was used as control (shControl) ([Redis et al, 2016](#)). Target sequences are as follows: shAgrin 5'-CCTGCTCTACAACGGGCAGAA-3' and shControl 5'-CAAGCTGACCCTGAAGTTCAT-3'. Procedures for packaging shRNA-encoding lentivirus were performed at the Viral Vector Laboratory (LVV, LNBio-CNPEM, Campinas, Brazil). We generated two cell groups: agrin silenced cells (shAgrin) and control cells (shControl). Agrin silencing was verified by real-time quantitative PCR (RT-qPCR) and western blot.

Generation of C-terminal agrin-overexpressing cells. We simulated a secreted bioactive fragment of agrin using the C-agrin_{4,19}-GFP construct ([Neuhofer & Daniels, 2003](#)) (Ct-agrin; Supplementary Figure 2A). This fragment was kindly gifted by Dr Matthew P. Daniels (NIH, Bethesda, MD, USA). We used as control a FLAG-tagged GFP (named IP-control) cloned into a pcDNA3 vector (Invitrogen, Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., MA, USA). Ct-agrin construction produced cytotoxicity in SCC-9 and HSC-3 cells (Supplementary Figure 2B). This problem was solved by transfecting HEK-293 cells using polyethylenimine (PEI, Polysciences Inc., PA, USA) (Supplementary Figure 2C).

Gene expression analysis. RNA isolation and RT-qPCR were performed according to previously published protocol ([Kawahara et al, 2014b](#)). Primers used in this study can be found in Supplementary Table S3.

Immunoblotting detection. Cell lysate and secretome isolation for western blot analysis were performed as previously described ([Kawahara *et al.*, 2014b](#); [Rodrigues *et al.*, 2017](#)) Antibodies used are listed in Supplementary Table S4.

Agrin and cancer-associated events:

Proliferation. HaCaT, SCC9 and HSC-3 cells either transduced with control shRNA or agrin shRNA (1×10^4 cells/well) were seeded in 96-well plates. BrdU labelling assay was performed as described ([Simabuco *et al.*, 2014](#)).

Migration and tumor cell invasion activity. Motility assays were performed as described ([Granato *et al.*, 2014](#)), with some modifications. For migration, we used 7.4×10^4 cells/well (HaCaT, SCC-9 and HSC-3) and 24-well chambers with uncoated 8-mm pore polycarbonate membranes. For invasion, we used 8×10^4 cells/well (SCC-9 and HSC-3) and 96-well chambers pre-coated with Matrigel Basement Membrane Matrix (BD Biosciences).

Cancer colony formation. Control or agrin shRNA-transduced SCC-9 and HSC-3 cells (5×10^3 cells/well) were cultured in six-well plates. The culture medium was changed every 2 days. After 9 days, cells were stained with 4% formaldehyde/ 0.005% gentian violet solution. Images were captured with an inverted microscope. We quantified colonies using ImageJ histogram tool (darkest pixels were analyzed).

Multicellular tumor spheroid formation. To simulate cancer cells in the blood or lymphatic circulation, we performed a three-dimensional tumor sphere culture. Control or agrin shRNA-transduced SCC9 and HSC-3 cells (6×10^5 cells/dish) were cultured in non-adhesive conditions, as described previously ([Rivera, 2017a](#)). The multicellular tumor sphere area was analyzed using the ImageJ particle analysis tool.

***In vivo* tumorigenesis and aggressiveness of lesions.** We utilized a murine orthotopic model for OSCC. Mice were randomly divided into the following 2 groups (n=8 animals in each): HSC-3 shControl and shAgrin. Then, 2.5×10^5 cells/tongue in 20 μ L of Matrigel were intra buccally implanted into the right lateral portion of the tongue. Animal health was monitored daily. After 21 days, tumor severity was established by presence of ulcerations and conventional histopathological examination. We evaluated the growth pattern, keratinization, cell morphology, angiogenesis, and vascular (intravascular tumor thrombus) and neural invasion.

Rescue-like experiments. To evaluate the specificity of agrin rescues the phenotypes, we exchanged the conditioned media from HSC-3 shControl and shAgrin cells in proliferation, invasion and wound healing assays. Conditioned media (10 μ g) from each group (hereafter called rescue-like medium and shAgrin medium, respectively) was added in serum-free media as described previously ([Kawahara et al, 2014b](#)). For wound healing experiments, 2×10^4 cells/well were used as described previously ([Rivera, 2016](#)).

Determination of agrin binding partners:

Immunoprecipitation. We used the secretome extract of Ct-agrin and IP-control cells. Immunoprecipitation was performed at 4°C with 2.5 µg of GFP antibody (#af4240, R&D Systems) in the presence of 30 µL of protein G-Sepharose 4 Fast Flow (GE Healthcare) for 2 h in a rocker. Sample proteins of 250 µg were added and incubated with the beads overnight at 4°C. The sepharose-bound proteins were washed with cold TBST. Bound proteins were eluted with 4X Laemmli sample buffer at 95°C for 10 min and resolved by 10% SDS–PAGE for subsequent western blot analysis.

Protein identification. From 3 independent experiments, we excised, reduced, alkylated, trypsin-digested and desalted 60 SDS-PAGE gel bands containing proteins of agrin complexes according to previous protocols ([Aragao et al., 2012](#)) (Supplementary Figure 2D). Tryptic digested peptides were identified in a LTQ Orbitrap Velos mass spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc.) according to previous protocols ([Aragao et al., 2012](#)). Identification of proteins was performed using MaxQuant ([Tyanova et al., 2016a](#)) and Perseus ([Tyanova et al., 2016b](#)) software, as described previously ([Winck et al., 2015](#)). For bioinformatics analysis, we focused only on proteins identified exclusively in the Ct-agrin group. See Supplementary file for further details and explanation.

Agrin interactome characterization:

Bioinformatics. We used Integrated Pathway Analysis Database for Systematic Enrichment Analysis (IPAD) ([Zhang & Drabier, 2012](#)) to evaluate the inter-association between our identified protein lists and diseases. In IPAD, Fisher Exact test is adopted to measure the gene-enrichment in annotation terms and the enrichment between

components. IPAD adjust the p-value by Benjamini-Hochberg method ([Benjamini & Hochberg, 1995](#)). We considered a strong model if oral cancer appeared within the top 5 ranked epithelial diseases. Agrin binding partners (Ct-agrin exclusive proteins) were described using FunRich ([Pathan et al, 2015](#)). Then, networks and hubs were visualized using Contextual Hub Analysis Tool (CHAT app) in Cytoscape software ([Muetze et al, 2016](#); [Rivera, 2017b](#)). To prioritize proteins, we used the cBio cancer genomics portal ([Cerami et al, 2012](#)) and HNSCC-TCGA dataset ([TCGA, 2015](#)) selecting the genomic profiles by default (mutations, putative copy-number alterations from GISTIC, mRNA Expression z-Scores [RNA Seq V2 RSEM] and protein expression Z-scores [RPPA]). To explore if prioritized candidates represent a community, we used the STRING database ([Szklarczyk et al, 2015](#)). In addition, we evaluated gene expression levels of agrin contextual hubs in shControl and shAgrin cells using RT-qPCR. The agrin group also was analyzed using SMART ([Letunic & Bork, 2017](#)) and PAZAR database ([Portales-Casamar et al, 2009](#)).

Overall survival data. We evaluated the prognostic potential of agrin contextual hubs. Gene expression data in head and neck cancers was obtained from the following publicly available databases: PROGgeneV2 ([Goswami & Nakshatri, 2014](#)) (GSE65858 dataset) and SurvExpress ([Aguirre-Gamboa et al, 2013](#)) (HNSCC-TCGA provisional dataset).

Statistics. All independent experiments were performed in triplicate. The results are presented as the mean \pm standard deviation (SD). We analyzed differences between groups using Chi-Square, Student's t-test, Fisher's exact test and one-way ANOVA

(with post hoc Tukey) tests. In all the procedures, we used a 95% confidence level (P -value ≤ 0.05).

RESULTS

Agrin is elevated in malignant and premalignant lesions. Oral cancer is a multi-stage disease ([Rivera, 2015](#)). We believe that its progression can be studied by comparing benign tissues, OEDs and malignant lesions. By immunohistochemistry, we detected higher expression of agrin in OSCCs (n=58) and OEDs (n=48) than in benign tissues (fibrous hyperplasia and hyperkeratosis, n=35) (Figure 1A and B). Epithelial staining intensity and reactivity were dichotomized, as shown in Figure 1C. To further investigate the clinical significance of agrin expression in OSCC progression, we examined the association between agrin staining status and patient diagnosis. The results indicated that high expression of agrin was associated with the presence of OEDs and OSCC (see relative risks in Figure 1D). These results may indicate that as cells increase agrin expression, the premalignant or malignant changes may become enhanced, shifting the balance from reversible status to tumor progression.

Agrin silencing suppresses cancer progression events, but conditioned media enriched with Ct-agrin rescue these effects. Most oral cancer cell lines secreted high levels of agrin (Figure 2A, right panel, band having a molecular weight of ~72kDa). We used shRNA technology to knockdown agrin expression in 3 cell lines. The knockdown efficiency of agrin shRNA was confirmed by RT-qPCR and dot blot (Figure 2B). Compared to non-target shRNA, treatment with agrin shRNA resulted in a significant decrease in cell proliferation, migration, invasion (Figure 2C) and *EGFR* mRNA levels (Supplementary Figure 3). Recent studies indicate that agrin provides stimulatory signals to augment FAK activity during cancer growth and invasion ([Chakraborty et al, 2015](#); [Chakraborty et al, 2017](#)). FAK induces cell cycle progression through cyclin D1, involving extracellular-signal-regulated kinase (ERK), among others

([Sulzmaier et al, 2014](#)). In OSCC cells, treatment with agrin shRNA reduced the levels of FAK and ERK phosphorylated forms, as well as, reduced the expression of cyclin D1 (Figure 2E). In addition, agrin silencing suppresses the colony and tumor spheroids formation (Figure 2D and E). Taken together, the data suggests that silencing agrin in oral cancer cells results in an impairment of *in vitro* proliferative and invasive growth programs. Next, we examined the effect of shControl secretome (conditioned medium), on cell migration, invasion and wound healing experiments. The results showed that exogenous shControl secretome rescues cell motility in agrin silenced cells (Figure 3A-B). Rescue-like medium had a higher capability to stimulate proliferation, invasion and wound healing compared to the secretome originating from shAgrin cells. These results demonstrate that progression of oral cancer may depend, at least in part, on the availability of agrin in the tumor microenvironment.

Agrin silencing reduces tumor aggressiveness. As shown in Figure 4A, mice that received agrin silenced cells (shAgrin) developed less aggressive tumors. These tumors did not have ulcers, instead they showed a well-defined mass tumor formation. According to the histopathological evaluation, shAgrin group produced smaller tumors with few instances of vascular and nervous invasion (Figure 4B). Tumors generated from control cells show significantly greater aggressiveness in comparison to tumors originating from agrin silenced cells. An additional panel of histological images can be seen in Supplementary Figure 1.

Agrin interactome reveals an enrichment in cellular growth process. To better understand how agrin participates in malignant progression, we aimed to identify proteins interacting with Ct-agrin in HEK-293 cells. After the immunoprecipitation

experiments, proteins bound to secreted agrin complex were identified by mass spectrometry. A total of 197 candidates exclusively interacting with agrin complex (Supplementary dataset 1). Since that the interactome of a protein can be highly cell-type dependent, we examined all interacting partners using the IPAD ([Zhang & Drabier, 2012](#)) with focus in malignant diseases. As shown in Figure 5A, tongue neoplasms are in the top 5 predicted protein-diseases related to agrin partners. We also submitted these candidate proteins to FunRich ([Pathan et al, 2015](#)) tool for functional analysis. We found that cell growth is the major biological category among the agrin-interacting candidates (Figure 5B). Interestingly, FunRich identifies the interaction between the growth receptor-bound protein 2 factor (GRB2, not identified in our LC-MS/MS experiments) with many candidates potentially associated with agrin (Figure 5C). The interaction of GRB2 with FAK and other proteins leads to activation of the Ras and ERK pathways, which induce tumor cell spreading through cytoskeleton rearrangement ([Giubellino et al, 2008](#)).

Prioritization of agrin interacting partners reveals the “agrin contextual hubs”. We assigned numeric values to all identified agrin interacting candidates as follows: -3 (Ip-control exclusive proteins), +3 (Ct-agrin exclusive proteins) and 1 (common proteins). Networks were visualized using CHAT app. Using a hypergeometric test CHAT identifies hub nodes that interact with more "contextual" nodes (i.e. Ct-agrin exclusive proteins) than statistically expected in networks integrated with user-supplied contextual data (e.g. gene expression data). CHAT term these nodes as contextual hubs. Contextual hubs are considerably more relevant than degree-based hubs to the specific experimental context under investigation ([Muetze et al, 2016](#)). Neighbor interactors were sourced from 4 databases (InnateDB-all, Mentha, IntAct, and UniProt). P-values

calculated by CHAT are automatically corrected using the Benjamini-Hochberg procedure. Then, we identified the most important centers of activity (the top 20 smallest p-values). To prioritize candidates, we used the cBio cancer genomics portal (2016 version) ([Cerami et al, 2012](#)). From that top 20, we chose those proteins that presented any alteration (amplification, deep deletion, mRNA up or downregulation, truncating or missense mutations) in a percentage equal to or higher than 20% of The Cancer Genome Atlas HNSCC sample (TCGA Nature 2015, n=279) ([TCGA, 2015](#)) (Supplementary dataset 1). We selected 9 proteins: cullin-1 (CUL1), cullin-5 (CUL5), eukaryotic initiation factor 4A-II (EIF4A2), protein NDRG1 (NDRG1), polyadenylate-binding protein 1 (PABPC1), dolichyl-diphosphooligosaccharide-protein glycosyltransferase subunit 1 (RPN1), double-stranded RNA-binding protein Staufen homolog 1 (STAU1), titin (TTN), and 14-3-3 protein zeta/delta (YWHAZ). Henceforth, we refer agrin and its 9 partners as the "agrin contextual hubs" (the function of each member is described in Table 1). Additionally, Supplementary Table S5 shows OncoPrints (distinct genomic alterations, including somatic mutations, copy number alterations, and mRNA expression changes) across a subset of OSCC cases.

Agrin contextual hubs can potentially modulate transcription factors. To explore if prioritized proteins represent a community (group of nodes with common processes, purposes, or functions), we used the STRING database ([Szklarczyk et al, 2015](#)).

STRING analysis resulted in a network with a high clustering coefficient (proteins have more interactions among themselves than what would be expected for a random set of proteins of similar size, drawn from the genome)(Figure 4C). To explore this relationship, we evaluated gene expression levels of the agrin contextual hubs in shControl and shAgrin cells. Surprisingly, agrin silencing affected gene

expression of different members of agrin group (Figure 5D). To explore whether agrin serves as a transcriptional regulator, we used SMART ([Letunic & Bork, 2017](#)).

According to prediction domain tools, agrin does not contain a DNA binding domain, however, it does not exclude the possibility that agrin modulates RNA expression, since it can bind to transcription or enhancer factors. Therefore, we have also evaluated if the transcription factors for the 10 genes overlap, which partially explains the gene expression regulation that was observed in agrin knockdown condition. Analyzing the transcription factors for agrin contextual hubs in the PAZAR database for gene regulatory information ([Portales-Casamar et al, 2009](#)), we observed that EGR-1 is the transcription factor for 9 out of the 10 genes in the agrin group (Supplementary dataset 1).

Agrin contextual hubs represent a community with prognostic potential. Since OSCC is the most common type of malignancy arising from the epithelial cells of the head and neck region ([Dahiya & Dhankhar, 2016](#)), we evaluated a clinical relevance of agrin contextual hubs in head and neck cancers. We used ProgGene ([Goswami & Nakshatri, 2014](#)) and SurvExpress ([Aguirre-Gamboa et al, 2013](#)) online tools in HNSCCs publically available gene expression databases. High agrin contextual hubs expression was associated with lower overall survival (hazard ratio 7.6, confidence interval 1.7-33.3, P -value ≤ 0.05) in a German cohort followed up for more than 5 years (GSE65858, n=269) ([Wichmann et al, 2015](#)) (Figure 5E). Similarly, in the HNSCC-TCGA provisional (SurvExpress, June 2016) dataset (by splitting 502 patients into two maximized risk groups according to their prognostic index), we found that high-risk patients had decreased overall survival (hazard ratio 1.6, confidence interval 1.3-2.7, P -

value ≤ 0.05) (Figure 5F). These results suggest that higher expression of agrin contextual hubs is associated with a poor clinical prognosis.

DISCUSSION

A class of molecules with relevant clinical potential, particularly for HNSCC, is heparan sulfate proteoglycans ([Farnedi et al, 2015](#)). They can be found on the cell surface and soluble in the ECM. Investigation of these molecules as participants in cancer progression is of great importance and reveals complex relationships occurring at the microenvironment, cellular and subcellular levels ([Soares et al, 2015](#)). In this study, we show that agrin promotes the progression of oral cancer and that its contextual hubs can predict a poor clinical prognosis.

We found that invasive oral carcinomas and premalignant lesions show a strong expression of agrin compared with benign lesions. We calculated relative risk to use as strength of association ([LaMorte, 2016](#)) and biopsies with high agrin staining have 2-7 times the rate of malignant or dysplasia diagnoses compared to samples with low staining. Previous research reported that immunohistochemical evaluation of agrin is useful to differentiate benign lesions, dysplasias and hepatocellular carcinomas ([Tatrai et al, 2009](#)). In fact, intriguingly, we observed the presence of cleaved or secreted agrin in oral cancer cell secretomes, but not in normal or immortalized cells. In addition, agrin can help distinguish between primary lesions of liver and metastasis with a high sensitivity and specificity ([Somoracz et al, 2010](#)). Oral cancer is a multi-stage disease, generated by sequentially malignant events, from epithelial precursor lesions to invasive carcinoma ([Rivera, 2015](#)). Considering the higher expression of agrin in dysplastic and malignant keratinocytes, and its secretion mainly by cancer cells, it could play a role and/or reflect the process of malignant progression. It was a surprise to identify secreted agrin as a band of ~72 kDa, since the proteolytic results of C-terminal fragment of agrin have molecular weights of ~135, ~110, ~90 and ~22 kDa. In a model that evaluated

Agrin expression in synaptogenesis induced by a traumatic brain injury, the authors found Agrin expressed only as species of a molecular weight between 75-55 kDa ([Falo et al, 2008](#)). They suggest that proteolysis may not be the major regulator of Agrin expression since fragments generated by MMP-3 and neurotrypsin were not observed. Recent evidence shows that Agrin is a target of several metalloproteinases, generating protein subfragments that can have diverse regulatory activities ([Patel et al, 2012](#)). The presence of ~ 72kDa agrin band in OSCC secretome may be due to an intermediate processing of known proteases, a cleavage performed by some other protease, or that some alteration in secreted agrin by aberrant squamous cells causes an atypical processing. The nature of this band should be clarified in future work.

To further explore these findings, here we present evidence demonstrating that agrin silencing interferes with oncogenic cell functions. This is consistent with our previous findings where agrin siRNA knockdown promoted a decrease on OSCC cell migration and adhesion ([Kawahara et al, 2014a](#)). Conversely, agrin rescue-like experiments restored proliferative and invasive behavior in agrin-silenced cells. The secretome is a relevant component for cell-cell communication and the cross-talk between tumor and stroma has a key influence on cancer progression ([Kawahara et al, 2014b](#)). Our results suggest that the observed cell phenotype may be due to the presence of agrin in the tumor microenvironment.

Moreover, in the context of liver cancer, agrin promotes proliferation, invasion and oncogenic cellular signaling ([Chakraborty et al, 2015](#)). The invasive and proliferative phenotypes constitute fundamental biological activities for the progression of malignant diseases ([Gao et al, 2005](#)), and agrin contributes in maintaining these phenotypes. Recent data have shown that FAK pathways are crucial downstream signaling axes of agrin function in liver tumorigenesis ([Chakraborty et al, 2015](#)). In our

experiments, we found that inhibition of agrin expression decreased pFAK, pERK and cyclin D1 protein levels. This clearly demonstrates the relationship between agrin and cell cycle progression promoted by FAK also in oral cancer cells. Notably, orthotopic tumors produced by agrin-silenced cells exhibited reduced aggressiveness, showing less vascular and neural invasion, which are associated with a better clinical prognosis ([Chi et al, 2015](#); [Tai et al, 2012](#)).

We used an immunoprecipitation-based proteomic approach to identify partners of secreted agrin. We discovered 197 proteins potentially interacting with agrin complex. These proteins are mainly related with cell growth, RNA and ubiquitin ligase binding processes. A close examination using FunRich tool indicated GRB2 (a member of FAK signaling pathway) as an interactor with many proteins potentially presented in agrin complex. It is evident that in OSCC cells, agrin can be a secreted or cleaved molecule and as a soluble fragment, agrin can bind to integrins or dystroglycan complex and then could activate FAK ([Bezakova & Ruegg, 2003](#)), which induces cell growth, invasion and metastasis through GRB2, SRC, ERK and cyclin D, among others ([Sulzmaier et al, 2014](#)). Our contextual analysis of potential agrin binding partners, immunopurified from the extracellular space, identified highly connected nodes located in the intracellular compartment. Within these nodes, we prioritized 9 hubs to construct the agrin contextual hubs: CUL1, CUL5, EIF4A2, NDRG1, PABPC1, RPN1, STAU1, TTN and YWHAZ. These proteins may interact directly or indirectly with secreted agrin. Agrin contextual hubs could interfere and enhance the FAK signaling pathway (a proposed model is presented in Figure 5H). For example, CUL1 is necessary for expression of SRC family kinases and FAK ([Bai et al, 2011](#)). Conversely, a low expression of CUL5 ([Teckchandani et al, 2014](#)) and NDRG1 ([Wangpu et al, 2016](#)) allows SRC and FAK activation.

According to our bioinformatics analysis agrin contextual hubs represent a biologically connected community. This was confirmed by changes in the expression profile of network members when agrin was silenced. For example, an increased expression of NDRG1 was observed in shAgrin cells compared to control cells. Interestingly, NDRG1 lower expression has been previously correlated with tumor progression and poor prognosis in patients with solid tumors ([Ando et al, 2006](#)). Then, we further investigated investigate how agrin expression affected gene expression of its contextual hubs. Surprisely, we observed using PAZAR database analysis that EGR-1 is a common transcription factor among all the members of the agrin group. In addition, to influencing agrin expression, EGR-1 is involved, either directly or indirectly, in the process of agrin cleavage ([MacDonald et al, 2017](#)). Agrin is known to activate FAK and it is a critical regulator of YAP/TAZ function ([Chakraborty & Hong, 2018](#)). A recent work indicates that YAP/TAZ are major oncogenes associated with OSCC ([Hiemer et al, 2015](#)). Since EGR-1 is a factor that also regulates the transcription of YAP and TAZ (according PAZAR database), it may be interesting to explore whether EGR-1 silencing affects tumor progression or if agrin depletion affects YAP/TAZ activity in oral cancer cells. In this way, further investigations are needed to elucidate the underlying mechanisms of agrin contextual hubs.

In this research, the histopathological data cumulatively support the pathophysiological role of agrin in oral cancer progression. On the clinical perspective, we demonstrated that patients with HNSCC that show a high gene expression of agrin contextual hubs have a lower survival rate. Since agrin is a gateway for a set of proteins with clinical relevance, it is plausible to think that agrin could be a potential therapeutic alternative for future research. In conclusion, our results underscore agrin expression as

a novel marker for malignant and premalignant oral lesions, and indicates agrin contextual hubs as a prognostic signature for head and neck cancers.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS. AFPL and CR conceived this research. CR and WAGA performed the clinical sample collection and classification. CR, FSZ, CSR, CD, DCG carried out experiments. CR analyzed data. CR and AFPL drafted the manuscript. All authors have read and agreed with the final version of the manuscript.

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TITLES AND LEGENDS TO FIGURES

Figure 1. Agrin is overexpressed in oral cancer and epithelial precursor lesions.

(A) Representative microphotographs of agrin immunohistochemical staining in oral tissues. Positive staining of agrin is shown in brown. Scale bars, 200 μm . (B) Stronger agrin score staining is observed in oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC) and oral epithelial dysplasia (OED) (ANOVA followed by Tukey's test). Data are present as the mean \pm SD (* P -value ≤ 0.05 , ** ≤ 0.001). (C) Intensity and geographical spread for agrin staining. Premalignant and malignant diagnosis can be correlated with the increase in agrin staining (visualized by black colored bars). (D). Expression level of agrin was closely associated with patient diagnosis (Relative risk; CI, confidence interval, Fisher's exact test). Agrin intensity and geographical spread were dichotomized as levels 1 and 2.

Figure 2. Agrin silencing decreased oral cancer progression *in vitro*, in less (SCC9) and highly (HSC-3) invasive OSCC cells.

(A) Western blotting confirmed the presence of agrin in different cell lines, both in the cell lysate and secretome. Multiple bands may represent proteolytic cleavage products, besides the alternative splicing variants and post-translational modifications. Vinculin, actin and ponceau red were used as loading control. (B) Verification of agrin silencing was performed by RT-qPCR and dot blotting. Actin expression was used as an internal control. (C) Agrin silenced cells (shAgrin) proliferate, migrate, and invade less compared to the control (shControl; absorbance at 450, 600 and 620 nm, respectively). (D) Agrin silencing decreased pFAK, pERK and cyclin D1 protein levels (E) Focus formation assay demonstrates less number of colonies in agrin silencing compared to the control. Darkest intensities are represented in millions of pixels. Scale bars, 2 cm. (F) Agrin silencing interferes with tumor sphere formation. Scale bars, 100 μm . Area in μm^2 (x100,000 to SCC9 and x10,000 to HSC-3). For all RT-qPCR experiments, data were normalized with *GAPDH* gene. Data are represented by the mean \pm SD of three independent experiments performed in triplicates (Student's t-test, * P -value ≤ 0.05 , ** ≤ 0.001).

Figure 3. Secretome containing agrin plays a role in cancer progression events.

In rescue-like experiments, HSC-3 shControl secretome (rescue-like medium) enhanced proliferation, invasion (A) and wound healing (B) in shAgrin cells. Data are represented by the mean \pm SD of three independent experiments performed in triplicates (* P -value ≤ 0.05 ANOVA followed by Tukey's test). Scale bars, 0.1 cm.

Figure 4. Agrin regulates the severity of oral cancer.

(A) An orthotopic model of OSCC was established, inoculating HSC-3 cells into the lateral border of the tongue of NOD-SCID mice. Animals received control (shControl) or silenced (shAgrin) cells. Representative images are shown (day 21). Scale bars, 0.2 cm and 400 μm (microphotographs). (B) Main histopathological characteristics of oral cancers are demonstrated above (* P -value ≤ 0.05 Student's t-test and Pearson's Chi-square test).

Figure 5. High expression of agrin contextual hubs predict poor prognosis.

(A) IPAD predicted diseases with exclusive Ct-agrin ligands as input. Cellular model was strong due to the presence of tongue cancers within the top 5 ranking (top neoplasms from 2,630 diseases). (B) Classification of biological processes of candidate proteins was performed by FunRich. A total of 197 candidates were analyzed. * Regulation of

nucleobase, nucleoside, nucleotide and nucleic acid metabolism. **(C)** FunRich identifies the interaction between GRB2 (predicted) with many candidates potentially associated with agrin. **(D)** Prioritized candidates using CHAT app and cBio cancer genomics portal. STRING clustering coefficient and protein-protein interaction (PPI) *P*-value are shown. **(E)** Agrin silencing in OSCC cells alters gene expression of agrin contextual hubs (data for independent replicates are presented in Supplementary dataset 2). **(F-G)** Analysis of HNSCC patient survival. Tumor samples that exhibit higher expression of agrin interactome show poor patient prognosis. F and G represent different cohorts. **(H)** A hypothetical model suggesting the role of agrin in oral cancer: i) overexpression of secreted or cleaved agrin triggers elevated binding to its receptors promotes FAK activation and ii) pro-tumorigenic activation of agrin contextual hubs could potentiate this pathway.

FIGURE 1

FIGURE 2

FIGURE 3

FIGURE 4

A

B

FIGURE 5

Table 1. Agrin contextual hubs. The function of each member is described below according to literature mining.

Protein (gene name)	Changes in mRNA expression*	Information
Cullin-1 (CUL1)	(+)	CUL1 and CUL5 provide a scaffold for ubiquitin ligases. They participate in the processes of ubiquitylation and neddylation, which lead to the degradation of tumor-suppressor proteins. ¹ Aberrant expression of CUL1 was found in a number of human cancers which is closely associated with poor patient prognosis. ²
Cullin-5 (CUL5)	(-)	CUL-5 expression is downregulated in breast tumors and its overexpression decreases breast cancer cell growth. ³
Eukaryotic initiation factor 4A-II (EIF4A2)	(+)	Boosts the malignant phenotype in solid tumors. ⁴
Protein NDRG1 (NDRG1)	(-)	It is associated with a low metastases rate. ⁵ In several cancers, it was suggested to be a tumor suppressor gene. Decreased expression of NDRG1 is correlated with tumor progression and poor prognosis in patients with esophageal squamous cell carcinoma. ⁶
Polyadenylate-binding protein 1 (PABPC1)	(+)	Can contribute to the aggressiveness of inflammatory breast carcinoma. ⁷
Dolichyl-diphosphooligosaccharide-protein glycosyltransferase subunit 1 (RPN1)	(+)	Forms part of the ubiquitin proteasome system. It is a structural component of the proteasome. ⁸ RPN1 has a significant association with an aggressive tumor phenotype in breast cancer. ⁹
Double-stranded RNA-binding protein Staufen homolog 1 (STAU1)	(-)	Stabilizes the mRNA in undifferentiated cells but can mediate its degradation in differentiated cells. ¹⁰ STAU1 overexpression affects mitosis entry and impairs proliferation of transformed cells. Participates in a mechanism of post-transcriptional regulation of gene expression that is linked to cell cycle progression in cancer cells. ¹¹
Titin (TTN)	(-)	Associated with mesoderm pluripotency in human embryonic stem cells. ¹²
14-3-3 protein zeta/delta (YWHAZ)	(-)	Shows high expression in patients with esophageal cancer, and it is associated with poor clinical prognosis. ¹³

*Tumorigenic gene expression according to the literature. (+) up-regulated/overexpressed, (-) down-regulated/down-expressed.

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SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

AGRIN HAS A PATHOLOGICAL ROLE IN THE PROGRESSION OF ORAL CANCER

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SUPPLEMENTARY METHODS

Mass spectrometry and data analysis. Tryptic-digested peptides were dried in a speed-vac instrument. The samples were analysed on a LTQ Orbitrap Velos mass spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., Waltham, MA, USA) connected to nanoflow liquid chromatography (LC-MS/MS) by an EASY-nLC system (Proxeon Biosystem, Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc.) through a Proxeon nanoelectrospray ion source as described previously. The raw files were processed using the MaxQuant and the MS/MS spectra were searched using the Andromeda search engine against the Uniprot Human Protein Database (UniProt release 2016_03, March 17th, 2016) with a tolerance of 20 ppm for precursor ions and 1 Da for fragment ions. A maximum of 2 trypsin missed cleavage was as set parameter for protein identification. Acetylation and oxidation were set as variable modifications, and carbamidomethylation was set as a fixed modification. Protein intensity values were normalized using the label-free quantification (LFQ) algorithm available through the MaxQuant program. It was used a 2 min window for matching between runs and maximum 1% peptide and 1% protein false discovery rate. Statistical analysis of the data was performed using Perseus version1.5 software. Protein identification datasets were pre-processed for the exclusion of contaminant entries, reverse sequences identification, and only identified by site entries. LFQ intensity values were log₂ transformed. The minimum valid values filter was set to 2 in at least one group. Three independent experiments were group in Ct-agrin and IP-control and a paired t-test was applied for testing of differences in protein intensities between these groups.

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES

Supplementary Figure 1. Histological features of tongue tumors. An orthotopic model of OSCC was established by inoculating HSC-3 cells into the lateral border of the tongue of NOD-SCID mice. (A-C) Tumors of HSC-3 shControl group showed an infiltrative growth pattern with discrete/absent inflammatory infiltrate. (A) Neural and (B) vascular invasion are common findings (arrows). (C) Cells demonstrated a spindle cell morphology. (D-F) HSC-3 shAgrin tumors showed well delimited growth, with muscular infiltration with moderate/intense inflammatory infiltrate. (D) Neural and (E) vascular invasion are uncommon findings. (F) Neoplastic cells demonstrated a cuboidal morphology and focal keratinization (arrows). Scale bars, 200 μ m. Lower panel shows the comparison between both groups (* P -value ≤ 0.05 Pearson's Chi-square test).

Supplementary Figure 2. Identification of C-terminal agrin partners. (A) C-terminal agrin-GFP construction was used as Ct-agrin in transfection experiments. (B) Non-viral vector transfection induced cell cytotoxicity in OSCC cells. (C) Overexpression of secreted protein (arrow) fragment in HEK-293 cells can be visualized by western blot. E1-E3 refer to 3 independent anti-GFP IP experiments that were done to identify Ct-agrin ligands (D) Ligands able to bind to Ct-Agrin (arrow) were silver stained in a 10% SDS-PAGE gel and the corresponding lanes were excised and analyzed by mass spectrometry. MaxQuant and Perseus were used for data analysis.

Supplementary Figure 3. Some expression factors involved in epithelial-mesenchymal transition are regulated by agrin expression.

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLES

Supplementary Dataset 1 and 2. Provided as XLSX files.

Dataset 1		Dataset 2	
Sheets	Title	Sheets	Title
1	Ct-agrin identified proteins	1	Figure qRT-PCR
2	IPAD validation	2	Z-score
3	CHATapp and Cbio portal	3	Means
4	PAZAR database		

Supplementary Table S1. Distribution of clinicopathological features in the study population.

Categories	Subcategories	Female	Male	Missing (gender)	Total
Diagnosis (n=133)	Hyperkeratosis	3	1	0	4
	Fibrous Hyperplasia	18	11	2	31
	Dysplasia	28	18	2	48
	OSCC	22	34	2	58
	<i>Total</i>	63	64	6	133
TNM* (n=56)	T1	5	4	-	9
	T2	6	11	-	17
	T3	4	9	-	13
	T4	7	10	-	17
	<i>Total</i>	22	34	-	56
	N0	13	21	-	34
	N1	3	6	-	9
	N2	5	5	-	10
	N3	1	2	-	3
	<i>Total</i>	22	34	-	56
Stage (n=56)	I/II	6	11	-	17
	II/IV	16	23	-	39
	<i>Total</i>	22	34	-	56
WHO differentiation degree (n=56)	Well	9	15	-	24
	Moderately	10	14	-	24
	Poorly	3	5	-	8
	<i>Total</i>	22	34	-	56
Pattern of tumor invasion (n=56)	Cohesive	9	18	-	27
	Infiltrative	13	16	-	29
	<i>Total</i>	22	34	-	56
Survival status (n=56)	Alive	9	19	-	28
	Deceased	13	15	-	28
	<i>Total</i>	22	34	-	56

*All patients were M0.

Supplementary Table S2. Cell lines used in this study.

Cell line	Information
HMK. Normal, non-tumorigenic. J Oral Pathol Med. 2016;45(9):704-11. Kindly donated by Dr. Tuula Salo, University of Helsinki, Helsinki.	Human oral mucosal keratinocytes obtained from surgical gingival biopsy and spontaneously immortalized. Culture conditions. Keratinocyte serum-free medium (Gibco, Paisley, UK) supplemented with antibiotics, 0,005µg/ml recombinant EGF, 0,5mg/ml bovine pituitary extract and 100µM of CaCl ₂ . Used as. Control group (RT-qPCR and WB initial experiments). Generated subgroups. None.
HaCaT. Normal, non-tumorigenic. J Invest Dermatol. 1997;108(1):78-82.	Non-tumorigenic keratinocytes originated from adult human skin. Culture conditions. DMEM (High Glucose, Sodium Pyruvate, L-glutamine and Phenol Red; Gibco) containing 10% FBS and antibiotics. Used as. Control group (RT-qPCR, WB, transduction, and functional experiments). Generated subgroups. HaCaT shControl and shAgrin groups.
SCC-9. Oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC). Cancer Res. 1981;41(5):1657-63. American Type Culture Collection, Manassas, VA, USA (ATCC).	Originated from human squamous cell carcinoma from the tongue. Culture conditions. DMEM/Ham's F12 medium (Cultilab, Campinas, SP, Brazil), supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS), antibiotics and 0.4 µg/mL hydrocortisone. Used as. OSCC group (RT-qPCR, WB, agrin-silencing and functional experiments). Generated subgroups. SCC-9 shControl and shAgrin groups.
SCC-25. OSCC. Cancer Res. 1981;41(5):1657-63. (ATCC).	Originated from human squamous carcinoma from the tongue. Culture conditions. DMEM/Ham's F12 with 10% FBS, antibiotics and hydrocortisone. Used as. OSCC group (RT-qPCR and WB initial experiments). Generated subgroups. None.
HSC-3. Metastatic OSCC. J Oral Maxillofac Surg. 2007;65(9):1725-33. Japan Health Sciences Foundation, Tokyo, Japan.	Human oral squamous cell carcinoma cell with high metastatic potential, from tongue. Culture conditions. DMEM/Ham's F12 with 10% FBS, antibiotics and hydrocortisone. Used as. Metastatic OSCC group (RT-qPCR, WB, agrin-silencing and functional experiments). Generated subgroups. HSC-3 shControl and shAgrin groups.
SCC9-LN1. Metastatic OSCC. Mol Cancer Ther 13:585–595. Kindly donated by Dr. Edgard Graner, UNICAMP Brazil.	The cell line was originated from SCC-9 cells isolated from mice lymph nodes (LN-1). Culture conditions. DMEM/Ham's F12 with 10% FBS, antibiotics and hydrocortisone. Used as. Metastatic OSCC group (RT-qPCR and WB initial experiments). Generated subgroups. None.

<p>HEK293. Unstable karyotype, variable tumorigenic potential. Gene. 2015;569(2):182-90. (ATCC).</p>	<p>Human embryonic kidney cells. After 65 passages it can form tumors in mice. Culture conditions. DMEM with 10% FBS and antibiotics. Used as. Experimental group (Generation of agrin-overexpressing cells and immunoprecipitation experiments). Generated subgroups. HEK-293 IP-control and C-terminal agrin groups.</p>
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*All cells were maintained at 37°C in a 5% CO₂ atmosphere. RT-qPCR, real-time quantitative PCR; WB, western blot; sh, short hairpin RNA; IP, immunoprecipitation.

Supplementary Table S3. Expression primers used in this research.

Name	Gene	Forward	Reverse
Glyceraldehydes-3-phosphate dehydrogenase	<i>GADPH</i>	5'- GAAGGTGAAGGTC GGAGTCAAC-3'	5'- CAGAGTTAAAA GCAGCCCTGGT- 3'
Agrin	<i>AGRN</i>	5'- TTGTCGAGTACCT CAACGCT-3'	5'- CAGGCTCAGTTC AAAGTGGT-3'
E-cadherin	<i>CDH1</i>	5'- ACAGCCCCGCCTT ATGATT-3'	5'- TCGGAACCGCTT CCTTCA-3'
Vimentin	<i>VIM</i>	5'- GGCTCGTCACCTT CGTGAAT-3'	5'- TCAATGTCAAGG GCCATCTTAA-3'
Cullin-1	<i>CUL1</i>	5'- CGCTGGCTTTGTG GCTGCTC-3'	5'- TGTGGCGGCTGG CGTAGAA-3'
Cullin-5	<i>CUL5</i>	5'- GAGTGGCTAAGAG AAGTTGGTATG-3'	5'- TCTTCTCTCATC CTTTCTGTAGTG- 3'
Dolichyl- diphosphooligosaccharide-- protein glycosyltransferase subunit 1	<i>RPN1</i>	5'- CACCTCAACAGT GGCAAGAAG-3'	5'- TGCATTTGCTC ACTCTGTCG-3'
Double-stranded RNA- binding protein Staufin homolog 1	<i>STAU1</i>	5'- TTTGTGACCAAGG TTTCGGTTGGG-3'	5'- TGGGCTTGTCTG TGGCTTGACTION- 3'
Eukaryotic initiation factor 4A-II	<i>EIF4A2</i>	5'- TTTTTCGGATCATGT CTGG-3'	5'- CAACTGTTGCAG GATGGA-3'
Polyadenylate-binding protein 1	<i>PABPC1</i>	5'- AGCAAATGTTGGG TGAACGG-3'	5'- ACCGGTGGCACT GTTAACTG-3'
Protein NDRG1	<i>NDRG1</i>	5'- GTGGTTGGGGACA GCTCGC-3'	5'- CAGCAGCACCCG AGTTGGGG-3'
Titin	<i>TTN</i>	5'- TCTATGATCGTTTT TGTGATACACGAA- 3'	5'- GAGCAAAGTGT AACGGCCAACA- 3'
14-3-3 protein zeta/delta	<i>YWHAZ</i>	5'- ATGTACTIONTGGAAA AAGGCCG-3'	5'- CCCTGCTCTTGA GGAGCTTA-3'

Supplementary Table S4. List of antibodies used in this study.

Antigen	Source	Dilution	Use*
Agrin	#sc-374117, Santa Cruz Biotechnology	1:300	IHC
Agrin	#sc-374117, Santa Cruz Biotechnology	1:500	WB
Actin	#ab3280, Abcam	1:2,000	WB
Vinculin	#ab18058, Abcam	1:1,000	WB
Green fluorescent protein (GFP)	#af4240, R&D Systems	1:10,000	WB
FAK	#sc-558, Santa Cruz Biotechnology	1:1,000	WB
Phospho-FAK	#44624-G, ThermoFisher Scientific	1:1,000	WB
ERK	#sc-153, Santa Cruz Biotechnology	1:1,000	WB
Phospho-ERK	#sc-7383, Santa Cruz Biotechnology	1:1,000	WB
Cyclin D1	#sc-374117, Santa Cruz Biotechnology	1:500	WB
Green fluorescent protein (GFP)	#af4240, R&D Systems Inc	2.5 µg	IP

*Recommended secondary antibodies were used. IHC, immunohistochemistry; WB, western blot; IP, immunoprecipitation.

Supplementary Table S5. Agrin contextual hubs in OSCC samples* (TCGA provisional dataset, n=320, February 2018).

TCGA information	Gene name									
	AGRN	CUL1	CUL5	EIF4A2	NDRG1	PABPC1	RPN1	STAU1	TTN	YWHAZ
Alterations (n=320)										
Without alterations	311 (97.2)	249 (77.8)	271 (84.7)	238 (74.4)	225 (70.3)	239 (74.7)	258 (80.6)	258 (80.6)	189 (59.1)	200 (62.5)
With alterations	9 (2.8)	71 (22.2)	49 (15.3)	82 (25.6)	95 (29.7)	81 (25.3)	62 (19.4)	62 (19.4)	131 (40.9)	120 (37.5)
Genetic profile (n=274)										
CNA										
Amplification	3 (33.3)		1 (2)	44 (53.7)	29 (30.5)	22 (27.2)	9 (14.5)		10 (7.6)	22 (18.3)
Deep deletion	2 (22.2)	4 (5.6)	4 (8.2)					1 (1.6)		
Mutation										
Missense mutation	3 (33.3)	3 (4.2)	2 (4.1)	1 (1.2)	1 (1.1)		2 (3.2)	2 (3.2)	98 (74.8)	1 (0.8)
Truncating mutation	1 (11.1)	2 (2.8)	1 (2)						17 (13)	
Inframe mutation									1 (0.8)	
mRNA										
Downregulation		37 (52.1)	26 (53.1)					9 (14.5)		
Upregulation		25 (35.2)	15 (30.6)	37 (45.1)	65 (68.4)	59 (72.8)	51 (82.3)	50 (80.6)	5 (3.8)	97 (80.8)
Survival (n=274)										
Living	5 (55.6)	33 (46.5)	27 (55.1)	36 (43.9)	45 (47.4)	41 (50.6)	34 (54.8)	33 (53.2)	59 (45)	69 (57.5)
Deceased	4 (44.4)	38 (53.5)	22 (44.9)	46 (56.1)	50 (52.6)	40 (49.4)	28 (45.2)	29 (46.8)	72 (55)	51 (42.5)
Survival (months)	18.7±15.2	33.4±21.7	25±17.6	26.6±22.8	30±25.5	32.5±27.3	30.2±19.1	32.4±21.6	30.7±22.1	35.4±29.2
Disease free	3 (42.9)	32 (72.7)	23 (60.5)	26 (51)	37 (52.9)	33 (54.1)	23 (54.8)	26 (59.1)	47 (54)	55 (61.1)
Recurred/progressed	4 (57.1)	12 (27.3)	15 (39.5)	25 (49)	33 (47.1)	28 (45.9)	19 (45.2)	18 (40.9)	40 (46)	35 (38.9)
Disease free (months)	16.3±16.3	33.3±21.8	21.8±18	24.7±23.6	27.5±26.8	29.4±25.5	27.2±20.1	30.4±21.9	27.5±22.9	31.9±28.1

Since 2017, cbiportal (<http://www.cbiportal.org/>) allows export cases according to specific anatomical sites (Oncoprint > add clinical tracks).

*OSCC includes: Alveolar ridge, buccal mucosa, floor of mouth, hard palate, lip, oral cavity and oral tongue. Parentheses indicate percentages within each gene. From 320 OSCC patients, 274 presented alterations. It is not possible perform a Cox regression, because exported variables are qualitative.